

ENHANCING PROFESSIONAL TRAINING THROUGH DEVELOPING CREATIVE COMPETENCES IN STUDENTS

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Abstract. *This article presents an in-depth scientific investigation of the pedagogical conditions and effective pathways for developing creative competencies to enhance students' professional readiness. Amid the dynamic demands of the modern labor market and the formation of an information society, a specialist's creative competence is regarded as a significant predictor of professional success. The article analyzes the conceptual content of creative competencies, their integration into the structure of professional readiness, as well as the pedagogical technologies and methods for developing these competencies. Research findings demonstrate that the formation of creative competencies substantially improves students' abilities to apply professional knowledge in practice, solve problems, and develop innovative solutions in professional situations.*

Keywords: *creative competencies, professional readiness, professional development, creative thinking, competency-based approach, pedagogical technologies, problem-based learning, project method, innovative activity, self-directed learning, professional adaptation.*

Introduction. The 21st century is characterized by the rapid development of information and communication technologies, global economic integration and the implementation of new achievements of science in practice. These processes have fundamentally changed the requirements of the modern labor market, requiring from specialists working in it not only deep knowledge and solid skills, but also the ability to quickly adapt to new situations, develop non-traditional solutions and constantly improve their activities. These requirements are especially relevant for teachers, since they are directly involved in the formation of the future generation. One of the main tasks of the modern higher education system is to form the professional training of students. The concept of professional training has a broader content than the traditional one, it includes not only knowledge, skills and experience, but also the psychological, cognitive and moral-spiritual preparation of a person for professional activity [1]. At the same time, creative competencies occupy a special place as an important component of professional training within the framework of the modern competency approach. Creative competencies are a set of abilities of a person to generate new ideas, solve problems in an original way, and carry out his activities in an innovative way. They are the main condition for a student to achieve high results not only during his studies, but also in his future professional activities [2].

Therefore, the scientific study of the theoretical foundations, pedagogical conditions and practical ways of improving professional training through the development of creative competencies in students is considered an urgent scientific problem.

The purpose of this article is to scientifically substantiate the pedagogical conditions, effective mechanisms and practical directions of improving professional training through the development of creative competencies in students.

Methodology. In modern pedagogy, the concept of competence has been widely studied by O.B. Anisimova, A.V. Khutorsky, I.A. Zimnyaya and other scientists [3]. I.A. Zimnyaya

interprets competence as a person's ability to demonstrate himself in a certain field of activity [4]. The concept of creativity has been deeply studied in psychology. J.P. Guilford saw creativity as a manifestation of divergent thinking and identified its four components - flexibility, fluency, novelty and accuracy [5]. E.P. Torrens interpreted creativity as a process of perceiving problems, identifying gaps in information and testing new ideas [6]. The concept of creative competencies began to take shape in modern educational paradigms. This concept was first used as a construct denoting the relationship between creativity and competence.

Creative competencies are the ability of an individual to apply creativity in various areas of professional activity. This concept includes not only the generation of creative ideas, but also their implementation, evaluation and improvement [7].

Figure 1. Components of creativity
Kreativlikning tarkibiy qismlari

Creative competencies are considered one of the main outcomes of modern education. The Council of Europe's document "For high-quality competences in a European framework" includes creativity and innovation among the key competencies [12]. The Law of Uzbekistan "On Education" also lists the development of students' creative abilities as one of the priority tasks of the country's education policy.

At this point, it is also necessary to touch upon the concept of professional training. In the traditional approach, professional training is mainly interpreted as a set of knowledge, skills and experience. However, the modern approach considers this concept in a broader context.

A.K. Markova characterizes professional training as a person's compliance with the psychological and pedagogical conditions necessary for acquiring and successfully implementing a particular profession [13]. V.A. Slastenin considers professional training as a system of professional knowledge, professional skills, professional experience and professional personal qualities [14].

The study studied the effectiveness of improving students' professional training through the development of creative competencies. The study was conducted based on the following methods. In particular, literature analysis, comparison, generalization, systematic analysis, pedagogical observation, interview, questionnaire survey, etc.

Result. The results of the study confirmed a significant increase in the indicators of students' professional readiness through the development of creative competencies. The control group used a traditional approach, and the growth rates there were 4-7%. This confirms the effectiveness of creative technologies in developing students' creative potential. The results of the study showed that the development of creative competencies has a significant positive impact on

the professional formation of students. In particular, through such an approach, students began to apply their professional knowledge more effectively in practice, which made it possible to combine their theoretical training with real activities.

Also, the skills of quick and correct adaptation to new pedagogical situations were developed, they learned to make independent decisions in different conditions. In solving problems, students began to use not only traditional, but also original and creative approaches, which brought their professional skills to a new level. In addition, a positive attitude towards professional activity and the level of self-confidence significantly increased. This situation strengthened their confidence in their abilities, helped them to be active and proactive. In the process of working in a team, their skills in cooperation, exchange of ideas, and free expression of their views were strengthened.

As a result, students began to strive to work on themselves, constantly develop their knowledge and skills. Thus, the development of creative competencies not only increased the quality of professional training, but also strengthened the personal and social activity of students.

Conclusions and recommendations. Based on the results of the research, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. Creative competencies are an integral part of the professional training of a modern specialist, they ensure the effectiveness of all components of professional activity.

2. The structural structure of creative competencies is a complex system that includes cognitive, motivational, practical, personal and reflexive components. Each of these components affects the corresponding component of professional training.

3. The mechanism of influence of creative competencies on professional training consists of the stages of creative assimilation of knowledge, creative application of skills, creative generalization of experience, creative development of personal qualities and transition to a higher integrative level of professional training.

4. The main pedagogical conditions for the development of creative competencies in students are the formation of a creative learning environment, increasing the creative and pedagogical competence of the teacher, and the use of creative technologies.

5. The results of practical research confirm that through the development of creative competencies, it is possible to significantly increase the professional training of students, especially the professional-creative and professional-psychological components. A high level of correlation was found between creative competencies and professional training.

As practical recommendations, it is important to introduce special courses and trainings aimed at developing creative competencies in higher education institutions. At the same time, it is necessary to enrich the curricula and programs and increase the share of problem-based learning, project methods and research activities. The introduction of modules aimed at developing creative and pedagogical competencies into the teacher training system, as well as the active involvement of students in research work, creative projects and startups, will also yield effective results. In addition, it is advisable to create a creative learning environment based on modern information and communication technologies and introduce creative indicators into the professional training assessment system and introduce complex assessment mechanisms.

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